

POLITICAL SCIENCE

Review

Vol. 14. No. 2, 2026

Published by:
Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria.

POLITICAL SCIENCE REVIEW

Vol. 14. No. 2, 2026

**A PUBLICATION OF THE DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL
SCIENCE, FACULTY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY
OF ILORIN, ILORIN NIGERIA**

E- ISSN 3121-9330

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Politics in the Migration of Nupe People into Ilorin Emirate in the Nineteenth Century

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Abstract

Migration is an important phenomenon in human life. From inception, Man wanders from one place to another to meet his needs, and since the want of Man is insatiable, the movement continues till eternity. Like others, the Nupe were sensitive to any situation that called for migration. The migration of the Nupe people into areas that are known as southwestern Nigeria today started with the establishment of the confederated Nupe States by Tsoede in the fifteenth century. The evolution of Ilorin as a caravan trade centre around the middle of the eighteenth century attracted several merchants, including Nupe war pieces of machinery, scribes, scholars, traditional doctors, fetches sellers, Berbers, brokers, and many other occupational groups. Thus, many Nupe immigrants had already settled down in Ilorin before the establishment of the Emirate. In accordance, the Nupe immigrants who were on the ground on the verge of the establishment of the Emirate government actively seized the opportunity to participate in struggles that led to the establishment of the Emirate Government. From a global perspective, politics cannot be overlooked as an essential factor that incited those Nupe migrants into Ilorin. In the migration history of Nupe into Ilorin, the factors of politics, which are locally, nationally,

and internationally recognised as important factors in human migration, have been downplayed. This paper, therefore, aimed to examine the political motivational factors that brought about Nupe migration into Ilorin, and their active participation in the establishment of an Emirate, which eventually qualified them to be recognised as a stakeholder. The paper adopted the historical research method, which involved the use of archival materials, oral interviews, text content analysis, and internet materials to assess the cause, courses, and consequences of the Nupe migration into Ilorin. The work concluded that politics played a significant role in the migration and settlement of the Nupe people in Ilorin, and such politics were also used as a mechanism to sustain the co-existence of the Emirate.

Keywords: Ethnic relations, Migration, Politics, Integration, Sustenance

Introduction

The pre-colonial political relations among the Nupe and other ethnic groups of the Niger River basin became noticeable to the Europeans in the colonial period. Having observed H. Barth's dialectic variation work on the people of the Niger areas, in his administrative periodical report to Ilorin Province, the Secretary (1921) of the Northern Province of Nigeria indicated scenarios of connections among the Nupe and their neighbours. He emphasised that Bidida (the ancient Nupe capital) superimposed on ...'Harghi country, which is located to Pindika, the Jukon capital in the Gombe region, which was by the Hausa called Dutsin Attagara- i.e the rock of the Attah (father) of the Gara (i.e Kwa or Kwara people) who in Jukon was called Asun (Nupe-Etsu)' (Circular, 1921, p. 156).

The Ilorin Emirate lies in Kwara State, which was created in the 1968 postcolonial era. Historical analysis shrouded in the above indentation suggests that the entire Ilorin Emirate area would have been denoted by

the suzerainty of Bidida since the precolonial period. However, several individuals from different fields from all over the world defined politics based on context. Among such, two selected relevant definitions to this work are that ‘politics is the way that people living in groups decide on an agreement that they can live together in groups such as tribes, cities, or countries’ (Simple English Wikipedia, n.d.). ‘Politics is not confined to a particular sphere but also occurs in every corner of human existence’ (Velari, n.d). Meanwhile, a description of politics that was established in the migration of Nupe people to Ilorin here discourses in the context of Nupe-Ilorin domestic issues, which culminated in factors that propelled the migration of the Nupe people from their pristine environment in the present Niger State of Nigeria to Ilorin, which is presently the State capital of Kwara State.

Based on such migration, this paper defines politics as: an indisputable subject of families’ relations, on which government and every other community/societal agent act to make decisions; a constitute of frequent value, which propels the essence of the social, economic and cultural life of people; and all intrinsic that every family acquires to formulate and sustain her social, economic and cultural life concerning other families, to project a nation for government and community/societal agent’s decisions. Given the above definitions, it is obvious that the affairs of all Nupe people who migrated to Ilorin are enshrined in politics. All politics of the Nupe and Ilorin families are here seen as National politics that were involved in the migration of Nupe people to the Ilorin Emirate and their settlement therein. In the 1960s, the second wave of feminist activism propounded feminist theory, which was captured in the slogan ‘the private is political or the personal is political’ (Politics, n.d.).

The slogan is here interpreted to mean that politics is enshrined in all private/personal and domestic issues that are relevant as a basis for the general politics of every pre-colonial, colonial, and post-colonial era of African States.

Migration of African people across other African nations is subject to domestic politics and issues, which Lee (1966) summarised and classified into ‘push and pull’ factors. The Nupe migration into Ilorin is noted here as a response to timely or periodical domestic/personal politics that occurred simultaneously in Ilorin and Nupe land, or separately in either State at different times. Favourable and unfavourable domestic issues in Nupeland coursed through general politics, which led to the emigration of some Nupe people to Ilorin, whereas enviable and well-conceived Ilorin domestic politics attracted the Nupe emigrants to settle in Ilorin as immigrants and later became integrated. Political relations among the Nupe and Yoruba were aided by several factors, among which was migration. In the second quarter of the twentieth century, correspondence between the Secretary's office of the Northern Province and the Ilorin Province resident confirms that the Yoruba from the southern part of Nigeria migrated to the northern part of Nigeria based on several basic agents such as physical, language, religion, and cultural relations.

The Eḍḍegi of Bida was pointed among the Sarakuna section of tribes from south to north (Lieutenant-Governor, 1921). Such migration of the Yoruba to northern Nigeria was said to be minor, compared to the great wave of mass movement of Hamitic (Yamanite) influence, which has been constantly progressive from North to South on both of the Niger Valley (Lieutenant-Governor, 1921).

Socio-cultural Contact, Relations and Migration: The Politics

Culture expresses the changing dominant interests involved in social, political, and economic conditions (Nadel, 1961, p.14). Some important factors that promoted relations, migration, and integration of the Nupe people into Ilorin included social and cultural activities, which had started during the period of Oranmiyan's contact with Elempe, the king of Nupe (Suleiman, 2018, p.242). The political expedition of Oranmiyan to Mecca to avenge the persecution of his ancestor was halted at the bank of the River Niger by the Nupe people. He was

subsequently having a privilege to establish the first Oyo seat at Ajaka in Nupeland. Perhaps, Oranmiyan was sensitive to unforeseen incessant attacks and possible destruction of his court by the Nupe people; he therefore applied the wisdom of politics by marrying Torosi, the daughter of Elempe, the king of Nupe. Relations and migrations of the Nupe people into Ilorin correlated with the socio-cultural stages of growth and development in both the Nupe and Ilorin political environments. The aspects of social-cultural activities that facilitated the migrations of Nupe to Ilorin are related to the efficiency of indigenous industries, religious freedom, exhibition of spiritual and cultural traits, festivals, and marriage to Ilorin people.

Industrial Migrants/Feudal Authority

Before the influx of Nupe people into Ilorin, the Yoruba and a few other linguistic families, such as Hausa, Kanuri, Malian, Ebira, and Nupe, were involved in indigenous industries, which included blacksmithing, cloth weaving, and dyeing, in Ilorin. Both in the pre-colonial Ilorin and Nupeland, blacksmithing was significantly associated with politics because the smith workshop produced war instruments, which were useful for the country's soldiers, either for the defense or expansion of the territory (Interview with Saliu Woru, 2019). The Nupe kings, feudal lords, and committed agriculturalists strengthened authoritative and diplomatic relations with the smiths to have credulous access to efficient war instruments and agricultural implements. Smith's works were censored and sometimes monopolised for competitive reasons. Materials that were censored in the pre-emirate Nupe-Ilorin industrial environment included war/farm implement and court regalia. Divulgence of materials' technical or spiritual secret of a particular stakeholder to another usually resulted in severe sanctions or even death of the smith. Three blacksmiths' workshops that existed in Ilorin in the pre-emirate period included Awodi (in the present Ilorin East Local Government Area), Oke-suna (in the present Ilorin West Local Government Area), and Gbodofu (in the present Ilorin South Local

Government Area of Kwara State). Awodi blacksmith workshop was said to have been established by Doshe, a Nupe man, the first noncommissioned Ilorin Army General (Interview with Jimoh, 2019). He combined Smith's work with warfare. When Afonja waged a defensive war (Ogidi war) against Ojo-Agunbambaru, the son of Bashorun Gaha of defunct Oyo, the former invited the latter as a mercenary. And Sheikh Alimi was at the rear of the war, in support of Afonja through the efficacy of prayer (Suleiman, 2021, p. 73).

Upon the success of Afonja, Sheikh Alimi established cordial relations with Doshe and enlisted him as a military general in the *Ogunadinimale* (sieged war) war against Majiya, Nupe war monger (Jimoh, 1994, pp. 79-83). It is important to note that at each of the wars fought by Doshe, the army of Nupe descendants migrated to Ilorin and were enlisted by Doshe to fight alongside other linguistic groups as Ilorin soldiers. At the end of the wars, some of the Nupe soldiers stayed in Ilorin to become Ilorin citizens, and their offspring are today known as Ilorites. A smith workshop that existed in Gbede (Oke Suna) before the arrival of Solagbru is significant to mention here, since it involved the presence of a Nupe descendant to whom the then Nupe immigrants might have secured lodging accommodation in anticipation of permanent settlement (Oral Interview with Saadu Giwa, 20/1/2006).

Response to Ilorin cloth weaving and dyeing industrial technological growth resulted in industrial migration among the Nupe cloth and dyeing industrialists and traders in the last quarter of the nineteenth century. The key to a decision by such a Nupe group was accentuated by Ilorin Emirate's political tact that had started accommodating the influx of immigrants since the establishment of the Emirate government in 1823. By the geographical location of Ilorin, it falls into the western part, and when it sought to be accommodated into the Caliphate in about 1823, it was automatically placed under Gwandu influence (Omoiya, 2004, p.38). Ilorin accommodated the influx of immigrants across the Niger Area as a measure to strengthen the population for

political and economic advantages. As part of the immigrants, the Yoruba and Hausa were proficient in their indigenous cloth weaving and dyeing production style. Over time, there was industrial contact among the three ethnic industrialists. The industrialists' relations would have instigated improvement in the quality of Ilorin textiles, such that Mrs. Marion Johnson's (John, 1973, p. 53) research indicated a diminution in demand for some types of Nupe cloth, and that Ilorin textiles took their place by the end of the nineteenth century. Reasonably, the textile proficient production and marketing popularity also attracted more Nupe immigrants into the Emirate.

Political Migrants

Of all the political factors that aided the migration of the Nupe and Nupe-Fulani into Ilorin, the impetus for religious zeal and dynastic feud is significant. Tsoede and four of his sons- Etsu Shaba (1559-1600); Etsu Zagula (1600-1625); Etsu Jiya (1625-1670); Etsu Moman Wari (1670-1679) (Idress, 1998, p. 20) ruled from Nupeko when it was the capital of Nupe land. In 1744, during the reign of Etsu Jibirilu, the Nupe capital was shifted to Raba. The location of Raba now exposed the Nupe rulers to the Okun land and the Igbomina land as well. In the early nineteenth century, the Nupe bent on invasion of Igbominaland, when Oyo's affairs were relatively controlled by Ilorin. Also, then, Ilorin had become an impregnable community to be incurred. Between the reigns of Etsu Jibirilu and Etsu Mua'zu (1744-1795), Nupe required greater economic power to sustain her administration.

However, the emergence of Islamic ideology in the northern hemisphere of Nupeland in the first decade of the Nineteenth century proliferated into the indigenous politics of Nupeland and triggered the precipitating wars among the rivals in the land. One important aspect of Nupe-Fulani relations is that there were neither permanent friends nor foes among them. For instance, Mallam Dendo, the father of Etsu Masaba (whose mother was a typical Nupe woman), was an ally of

Majiya against Jimada. However, Maliki (a Fulani Mallam) settled in Jimada's country without a crisis, although his position was clearly mentioned when the war between Jimada and Majiya was on. After his victory over Jimada, Majiya turned against the Fulani, including Mallam Dendo and Idrisu, son of Jimada. Dendo, Idrisu, and Maliki later became associates under the protection of Alimi and Tswado (a smith), Idris (son of Jimada), Mallam Baba, Mallam Dendo, Mallam Musa, and hundreds of Nupe migrated to Ilorin to seek asylum under the protection of Sheikh Alimi. The first politico-Islamic Nupe war took place in c. 1810 (Mason, 1981, p. 26); perhaps it was the same year when the fugitives migrated to Ilorin. Apart from Tswado, the fugitive group leaders who returned to Nupeland after Majiya was defeated in *Ogunadinimole*. Tswado's loyalists and some Nupe soldiers did not return to Nupeland but stayed in Ilorin to establish families that existed in Kutijifu, Gbodofu, and other quarters in Ilorin to date.

The lessons of those abortive invasions checkmated the Nupe against Ilorin; they were compelled to look for alternative 'colonies'. In addition, going by one of the colonial masters' reports, there is a suggestion that, before he invaded Ilorin in Sheikh Alimi era, Etsu Majiya firstly occupied part of the northern frontiers of Ilorin, and it is not undisputed that northern frontiers were sparsely populated by Nupe people, whereas the landowners, who happened to be the *Baalès* (chiefs) under the Alaafin were dislodged by Majiya's military. Burnett reports that:

On the arrival of the Fulani, to escape the war and in some cases to regain land which had been laid waste by Majiya, the Nupe war-monger, many of these small chiefs came to Ilorin and put themselves under some Balogun or leading men, and induced them the sanction of the Emir for their return to their lands (Hermon-Hodge, 1929, p.169).

The aforementioned lands or frontiers covered the whole present location of Jebbaland, Ilorin East Local Government Area, and Moro Local Government Area of Kwara State. And parts of the L.G.As share boundary limits with the River Niger, which is between the Niger and Kwara State of Nigeria. For Political protection as well as economic purposes, the Baaleş (chiefs) of Agbaku and Aribi (in the present Moro L.G.A) were among those that were holding the land before Majiyya's invasions (Interview with Suleiman, 2005). One of the results of the abortive invasion of Majiyya against Ilorin was that those people that vacated the lands that were earlier held by them returned therein permanently. Also, when the Yoruba Baaleş returned, some of their initial Nupe associates were later accommodated. There is evidence to prove that they returned to their respective lands after the invasion, because, to date, the descendants of those people are still holding estates both in their initial villages and in Ilorin metropolis. In fact, Leith-Ross discovered that:

...so constant is the movement between town and country; most families have both a compound in the town and a farm in the bush, and migrated from one to the other for two, three, or four months at a time, (Hermon-Hodge, 1929, p. 104).

Environmental and Climatic Factors

Politics involves mediation and actions in life. Environmental and Climatic Factors cannot be ruled out as part of the reasons for the emigration of Nupe to Ilorin. Many parts of Nupeland are located in the lowland along the location of the River Niger. The River produces high humidity in the climate, which may not be conducive to the health of some natives. Some of the Nupe immigrants in Ilorin were driven out of the Nupeland by outbreaks of diseases such as rheumatic fever, malaria, bilharzia, among others. The migration of some of the Nupe people to Ilorin in the Nineteenth century was related to climatic diseases. Many of those who were afflicted with diseases attributed the causes to spiritual attacks rather than environmental or climatic factors; therefore,

they followed the prescriptions of many of their clerics and native seers to live in their Nupelands (Interview with Hassan Aliu, 2019). Diseases that were emitted by the River, environment, and vegetation to the climate also affected some livestock and native animals of Nupe. Among all the animals, horses and cattle were very important to the Nupe aristocrats in the late Eighteenth and early Nineteenth centuries. A vivid description by Nadel (1961) indicated that, apart from the northernmost part of Nupeland, horses and cattle were not really saved from tsetse and trypanosomiasis diseases.

Ilorin, the southernmost of the Nupe country, was favourable to horses breeding and cattle rearing (Nadel, 1961, p. 4). Against this backdrop, a few nineteenth-century Nupe aristocrats and horse/cattle merchants depended on the Ilorin environment for the upkeep of their lives and the animals'. However, in 1926, climatic/environmental degradation was proven in Ilorin through the outbreak of tsetse infection, the consequence of which was sickness and mass death of cattle (Gavid, 1977, p. 16-18). Several Ilorin cattle herders migrated to Lafiagi (Nupeland), and by 1928, there was a rapid increase in herder penetration into Pateigi Emirate (Nupeland) (Elphinston, 1929, p. 40). It is imperative to mention that most of the herders had been integrated into the Ilorin community before migrating back to the Nupeland. Before such migration, they resided in the areas that included Akata Tanke, Alalubosa, and Ogidi (Interview with Aminat, 2019).

There was a reversal of Nupe-Ilorin migration between 1934 and 1935, when a great number of Nupe people migrated to Ilorin as an economic refuge. In those years, it was said that Nupeland experienced a great famine. The occurrence of the famine is established because it was recorded that there was a nadir of economic depression in Northern Nigeria between 1933 and 1934 (Nadel, 1961, p. 11). Perhaps, the 1932-33 economic depression of the United States of America and the 1933-34 economic depression of northern Nigeria were politically connected. Between 1934 and 1935, there was a great famine across all

of Nupe land. If famine resulted in Nupeland as a consequence of the proliferation of economic depression from northern Nigeria, and northern Nigerian economic depression is linked with that of the United States, it is, however, suggested that the 1934-5 wave of Nupe emigration to Ilorin was inevitable. Nadel expresses that in 1934-5, the Nupe community of Ilorin and Ibadan demonstrated a big wave of Nupe emigration in their towns. His expression was buttressed with a sample of 200 Nupe people that migrated from Bida Emirate, as the information was directly related to him (Nadel) from the District Officer, Bida Division (Nadel, 1961, p. 11). The following table shows the population of the Nupe people in Bida Emirate, Bida town, Ilorin Province, and Niger Province in 1921, 1931, and 1934.

It is deduced from the above table that there was a higher proportion of Nupe people in Ilorin province than in Bida town. No figure of Nupe population in Niger was even recorded in 1934. This was a result of the famine.

Crises in Nupeland and Ilorin-Gwandu Mediation

The return of Fulani-Nupe fugitives to Nupeland opened a new brand of crises and politics between themselves (Nupe-Fulani and Nupe origin fugitives). The crises and politics fascinated mutual permeable migration across geographical places in the Niger areas, of which Ilorin is not an exception. It should be remembered that Mallam Dendo, of Fulani descent, was able to conspire with Idirisu, Manzuma, Mallam Baba, and Maliki, with the alliance of Ilorin into a faction against the precipitant warring of Majiya. And Majiya was defeated. When they returned to Nupeland, each leader decided to establish an autonomous political entity, which favoured or disfavoured some groups of followers. The disfavoured followers of any of the Nupe groups moved to the other, while those who were not in support of any of the Nupe groups migrated to areas that included Ilorin. This is because, at this period, Ilorin's politics were harmonious to accommodate several migrants. Mallam Baba and Mallam Dendo, among all the leaders,

concretized the autonomy of their separate political enclaves by obtaining recognition from Gwandu and demanded a flag from Sokoto and Gwandu, respectively. At the time the flags were received, they were already aged. On this ground, they relinquished the thrones to their sons, that is, Mallam Baba to Abdullahi and Mallam Dendo to Usman Zaki. Elderly uncles and cousins saw the decisions as unjust; therefore, they started rebellions against the Etsus. Specifically, Usman Zaki's rulership was antagonised by Massaba, because the latter believed that the former was not eligible for the throne, since he was born to Mallam Dendo, their father, by a Fulani woman, Adama. Massaba was born to a Nupe woman, Fatima (Jimoh, 1994, p. 161).

Masaba, with his army, besieged Rabbah for a whole year. Ilorin attempted to rescue Usman Zaki, but Masaba had already chased him out before Ilorin's arrival. Although Masaba's wife was the Ilorin Emir's daughter, he became wanted. Meanwhile, at a time when escape seemed impossible for Masaba, Usman Yerima dragged Masaba's wife and told her that he would restore her to her father, the Emir of Ilorin, as her husband's days were numbered (Hermon-Hodge, 1929, p. 107). An allegation was leveled against Usman Zaki that he was lording it over "two rival Nupe factions, each of which had its own Etsu," the two factional rulers were Idirisu and Majia, who were compelled by Usman Zaki to pay taxes. Idirisu was reigning at Gbara, while Majia was at Zuguma. Usman Zaki laid claim to superiority over Idirisu because it was his father, Mallam Dendo, who aided him to become established as Etsu Nupe at Adama Lelu' (Jimoh, 1994, p. 158). He deemed it fit to impose authority on Majiyya, since Majia was a defeated foe of the 'allies'. The above lingering crises were exacerbated by Usman Zaki's appointment of Momodu Gborigi as Yerima of Raba. He was a grandson of Mallam Dendo and a nephew of Massaba. Massaba sought and got the alliance of Majia and Idirisu to overthrow Usman Zaki, but instead of getting him overthrown, they were dastardly dealt with, and as a result, Majia fled to Zuguma, Idirisu to Echu, and Massaba to Lade. Internal strife persisted until Tsado, the son of Majjigi, succeeded his

father at his demise. He reawakened the hostility between Usman Zaki and his father. This resulted in protracted chaos in Nupeland, and it was indeed called for mediation by Ilorin and Gwandu. Emir Shitta of Ilorin pleaded with the Emir of Gwandu, Halilu, for mediation in Nupeland. The latter yielded and

arrived at Raba and sent for the following chiefs to meet him there and discuss the situation:- Usman Zaki from Agaie; Abdullahi, Emir of Agaie; Shitta Emir of Ilorin; AbdulKadir, Emir of Lafiagi, from Ilorin; Masaba from Lade; Aliu Emir of Shonga, and Beji, Emir of Lapai. Also, the two Nupe Etsuzhi-Tsado, son of Majia, and Isa, son of Idirisu. All collected at Raba (Dupigny, 1920, p. 7).

The meeting was convened and chaired by the Emir of Gwandu. By the authority of the Emir, the ratification of the meeting was anchored on the deposition of Usman Zaki from the post of Serkin Fulani, and to exile him to Gando. In consonance with this, Masaba was enthroned as the Emir of Nupe. In addition, AbdulKadir, Emir of Lafiagi, was to be exiled alongside Usman Zaki to Gando, but Halilu's proposals were influenced by a plea from the Emir of Ilorin and Masaba; thus, he was left merely as the Emir of Lafiagi while all the lands in his possession were revoked to Masaba. Halilu toured Ilorin, and a host of Nupe people went with him, but not all of them left with him. He also toured Lade, Gbara, and Lafiagi, and when he was returning to Gwandu, he took Usman Zaki with him and dropped him at Gando (Dupigny, 1920, p. 7). The intervention of Halilu and Ilorin was quite recognised as politics without bloodshed.

The power vested in Masaba led to excesses in some of his administrative decisions. He was ruling without the due consultation of the chiefs in his political environment. As a result of this, he became unpopular among the chiefs and his subjects. A gallant officer (Mayaki

Uma, also known as Umar Bahaushu) member of his army, seized the opportunity to assemble a successful rebellion under Etsu Maza against Masaba. Masaba fled. The Emir of Ilorin, Oba Shitta, intervened once more to arrest the situation, but all persuasive efforts by him to bring Masaba to his senses failed (Jimoh, 1994, pp. 163-164). Masaba eventually retreated to Ilorin with his followers. Umar Bahaushu's victory intoxicated him by declaring himself Serikin Nupe, and charging the Nupe and Fulani of the land tributes.

He was checkmated by a call from Umar Majigi. Umar Majigi requested the Emir of Gwandu that Usman Zaki should be sent to Nupe as Serikin Nupe. Also, he sent to the Emir of Ilorin for the release and support of Masaba. Before he was approved to return to Lade, he observed a term with Ilorin. Elphinstone (1921) confirms that for 50 slaves, according to Ilorin tradition, Masaba was assured continued possession of the Lade country, which by right of prior claim, if not by conquest, belongs to Lafiagi. Masaba was given a warm reception by Ilorin. He was supported with types of machinery from Ilorin and hurriedly persuaded to leave the community because the ruling class and the chiefs were not in good trust with him, so he could not attempt to hijack the government (Bowen, 1857, p. 197). Masaba returned to Bida with troops from the south (Ilorin), supported by Usman Zaki and Umar Majigi, and with the assistance of the king of Bida town and the twelve Beni towns, Bahaushu's army was defeated, and he was killed after three months siege of Bida. Henceforth, the Nupe environment became a peaceful one. The alliance and the killing of Umar Bahaushu are akin to politics with bloodshed.

It should be remembered that there had been succession disputes between Masaba and Umar Majigi since about 1845. The political crises lasted till the 1870s before Oba Aliyu's (Emir of Ilorin) intervention. The Emir provided military assistance to his Nupe counterparts to quell the civic strife in their (Nupe) domains. Also, when Etsu Ibrahim Halilu prosecuted the war against Igbara, he was assisted by Maiyaikin,

Ilorin, and Otun Balogun Ibadan with 1,000 gunmen, and after conquering Igbira, Umar Majigi returned to Bida (Mason, 1981, pp. 81-82). However, after the allies had recorded success in their expeditions against the Ebira, Oworo, and Kabba, Ilorin cunningly annexed Ekiti and halted Ibadan's aim of extending the political authority to Ekitiland, while Ikole was also conquered out of the reach of Ibadan (Elphinston, 1929, p. 41). Ilorin's victory in sidelining Ibadan away from those areas could also be seen as a remote cause of the active participation of Ibadan in the celebrated battle of Ikirun, otherwise called the Jalumi war.

Nupe-Ilorin Joint Raids on Igbomina and Okunlands

Ambrose (1911) described politics as a union of two thieves who have their hands so deeply inserted in each other's pockets that they cannot separately pilfer a third. Perhaps, the administrative desire of Umar Majigi (one of the nineteenth-century contending Nupe leaders) was to establish a confederate colony. However, between 1873 and 1882, through pacification and diplomacy, he won the alliance of Ilorin and subjugated virtually the entire northeast of Yorubaland under Nupe (Jimoh, 1994, p. 427). The alliance enabled affectionate contact between the Nupe army under Umaru Majigi and Ilorin. Such contact provided an avenue for Nupe who wished to migrate to Ilorin, and indeed, some of them migrated. Abdullahi Nda of Alalubosa (now beside Government Secondary School Ilorin, Ilorin East LGA) was said to have migrated to Ilorin in the late Nineteenth century, after living in Umar Majigi war camp in Okunland (Interview with Ibrahim Abdullah, 2022). The Nupe's *Ogba* system covered the northeast of Yorubaland, with the inclusion of some Igbominalands. At the same time, Ilorin had already entrenched her political influence and authority on the Igbomina southwest, through the imperial administrative system, *Ajia* and *Maiyaki* (Apata, 1992, p.4). However, since the reign of Oba AbdulSalam (1816-1842) *Ajia* Gaju and Ali Balogun (who died in c.

1845) had conquered and annexed Ajase, Oke Ora, Yara, and Orangun as Ilorin colonies.

Several times in the Nineteenth century, Nupe, Ilorin, and Ibadan engaged in political expeditions to Igbomina and the Kukurukuland (Akoko, Ijumu, Oworo, Kakanda, Auchi, and Igbira now in North-central Nigeria) for economic and political reasons. As a result of this, Nupe and Ilorin established foreign policies and alliances, which facilitated more emigrational idealism. It is imperative to infer that the Nupe had had the earliest contact with Igbomina since about Sixteenth century, because it was said that Alaafin Ojigi was bent on checking their incursion through the appointment of Laderin as a resident in Ilorin. It has been suggested that the Igbomina area was inhabited earlier by the Nupe (Mason, 1981, p. 102). Over time, the Nupe were dislodged and partially absorbed by successive waves of Yoruba immigrants from Ile-Ife and then from Oyo-Yoruba speaking areas (Aboyeji, 2015, p. 98).

Yet, after a long period of time, the Nupe were found of attacking and chasing the Igbomina people out of the territory. In the middle of the eighteenth century, both Nupe and Ilorin sustained their relations on Igbomina affairs, based on diplomatic approaches, because the Igbomina land was taken as a pact theatre. Umar Majigi, a Nupe warlord, and Emir Aliu of Ilorin sustained the pact, and the alliances engendered variations of relations, such that some of Ilorin soldiers that were found in Umar Majigi's army were more comfortable to reckon with the troop than the Ilorin troop, while some Nupe soldiers preferred Aliyu's army. Those who decided to stay with Aliyu's army arrived in Ilorin with the army to establish a permanent family in Ilorin Emirate. For instance, Alidu, the compatriot of the ancestor of Alalubosa village in Ilorin East LGA of Kwara State, was said to be one of them (Interview with Bolakale, 2016).

Civil Service

The Royal Niger Chartered Company (RNCC), West African Frontier Force (WAFF), Colonial Administration, and the establishment of civil service in the post-colonial era yielded factors that facilitated the migration of Nupe people to Ilorin Emirate. In January and February 1897, Nupe and Ilorin were respectively conquered by the Royal Niger Chartered Company's army. Hence, Ilorin, Bida, Pateigi, and Lafiagi came under the control of the company. And by the end of 1897 West African Frontier Force (WAFF) strengthened its diplomacy with the Ilorin Emirate to facilitate the economic and political interests of the European. By the creation of Ilorin Province and Middle Niger Province in 1900, the political struggle of both Nupe and Ilorin Emirate, which the European saw as a trade impediment, was eradicated, and official migration became part of the new government bureaucracy.

Nupe Judiciary officers, trade/commercial representatives and officers, railway workers, and WAFF officers were posted to Ilorin Emirate. Some of them established family relations, which have lasted till today. For example, Alfa Yahaya, a Nupe descendant, the ancestor of Ile Pánù at Pataki, Ilorin, was said to have arrived at Ilorin around 1889. Between 1890 and 1905, as a judge, he traversed Ilorin and Lafiagi, and by c. 1909, he was officially posted by the Colonial Provincial Administration from Bindofu, in Lafiagi, to Ilorin Emirate. He was versed in Sharia knowledge. He was one of the judges of the Emirate in the colonial period. He judges at Ilorin, Igbaja, and Share. He retired from his post while at Share in the reign of Oba AbdulKadri. To date, Alfa Yahaya's offspring are bona fide members of the Ilorin community. In addition, S.D. Yusuf (2016) categorised the coming to Ilorin and relations of Alhaji Jimada Patigi, Alhaji Shafihi Tsaragi, Alhaji Jibirilu Taka Patigi, and Alhaji Ishaq Turakin Lafiagi (work master) under "the later Nupe settlers in Ilorin" (Yusuf, 2016, pp. 68-73). This is because they came to Ilorin as Public Servants. Their presence in Ilorin contributed to the existing pattern of relations

between Ilorin Kutigifu/Okesuna Nupe and other ethnic groups of Ilorin. Alhaji Jimada Patigi's processes of integration into Ilorin is recorded across his role as: a teacher in the defunct Provincial Secondary School (P.S.S.) Ilorin (in 1930s); the head teacher of Okesuna Elementary School (1943); a bosom friend of Mallam AbdulKadri, the Eighth Emir of Ilorin; a promoter of girl child education in the Emirate; a promoter of Adult Education (1963-1966); and a productive farmer both in Ilorin and Patigi (before his death in December, 12th 1989), among his other achievements (Yusuf, 2016 pp. 68-73). One of the cardinal points of sustaining Nupe-Ilorin integration through the gesture of Alhaji Jimada Patigi, Alhaji Jibirilu Taka Patigi, and some Nupe Muslim Public Servants in Ilorin in the Twentieth century is that the *Tafsir* at Jimada's house encompasses active roles of even those who are not of Nupe extractions. For instance, the Ile Arowasi, Ile Onileke, and Alhaji Armiyau families (all from the Kutijifu and Okesuna areas) are well represented in principal positions within the *Tafsir* protocol (Yusuf, 2016, pp. 68-73).

Findings

The findings of this work were that:

- i. domestic politics in both Nupeland and Ilorin Emirate are rooted in all factors responsible for Nupe migration into Ilorin Emirate,
 - ii. Nupe migration into Ilorin Emirate aided the strength of Ilorin politics,
 - iii. the Nupe immigrants in Ilorin are politically, economically, culturally, and socially related to other linguistic groups to promote the growth and development of the Emirate, and
 - iv. European administration contributed to Nupe's migration into the Ilorin Emirate.
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Conclusion

Ilorin Emirate is one of the heterogeneous communities in Nigeria. Its heterogeneity features since 1823, when she asserted sovereignty. Several ethnic groups across the Niger Area trooped in, and the Nupe people were not exempted among those who swelled up the Emirate population. Before 1823, history recalls that the Nupe people had engaged in several relations with the Ilorin people, but the establishment of the Fulani dynasty in that year facilitated the mass movement/settlement of Nupe and their political, economic, cultural, and religious contributions to the sustenance of the Emirate. The Nupe migration into Ilorin Emirate is perpetual since some of them also migrated and settled in Ilorin in the Post-colonial period. By and large, several descendants of Nupe immigrants in Ilorin have integrated as an essential body of the cosmopolitan Emirate. These migrations were driven by political factors, which influenced social, cultural, economic, and environmental/climatic conditions, among others.

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